

ISic0127

I.Sicily inscription 0127

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. C(aius) · Alfius · Cel[---]

2. vixit · ann(is) [---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Gaius Algius Cel[...]. He lived [...] years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285294

EDR 127517

EDCS 10900640

Bibliography

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese.

Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica. Palermo / Rome. At 46
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 327
Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis
inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici
Romani. Berlin. At VIII 699

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